

SCIENTIFIC-PEDAGOGICAL FOUNDATIONS OF DEVELOPMENT OF ENVIRONMENTAL COMPETENCE OF STUDENTS

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Abstract: This article analyzes the issues of developing environmental competence of students and describes the scientific and pedagogical basis.

Key words: competence, ecological education, reproductive, alternative, retrospective, ecological competence, competence, pedagogical.

INTRODUCTION

Today, the development of environmental competence among students is gaining relevance. The importance of ecological competence in students' formation of ecological worldview, high moral attitude to nature and environment, and increase of moral responsibility is high. Therefore, it is one of the urgent tasks to form and develop environmental moral values in students based on ecological competence and to grow their knowledge and skills based on historically formed national ecological values.

Issues of environmental education are gaining relevance in Uzbekistan. The growing global environmental crisis, environmental pollution and other problems require the eco-movement to become an active force.

LITERATURE ANALYSIS AND METHODS

Pedagogical aspects of the foundations of environmental education, the causes of environmental risks in the era of globalization, ways to eliminate them, scientific research aimed at developing some aspects of environmental competence in students Q. Abdurahimov, I. Kh. Ayubova, P. Berdanova, N. Bozorova, R. Kh. Djurayev, Y. Ahmadaliyev, N. Isakulova, Sh. Kamolkho'jayev, A. Malikova, M. E. Musayeva, V. Nikitin, N. O'. Nishonova, H. Norbo'tayev, T. Saparov, V. N. Sattorov, H. Togayev, E. O. It was carried out by Turdikulov, U. Turdikulov, D. Tokhliyev, A.S. Tokhtayev, A. Ergashev, Sh. Yunusova.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION.

"The most important issue is that we must seriously focus on improving the environmental culture of the population. Of course, such problems cannot be solved only by administrative means, it can be achieved by cultivating love for mother nature in the hearts of the young generation, a sense of belonging to it" [1]. Because "we have set a goal to turn Uzbekistan into a developed country, we can achieve this only with rapid reforms, science and innovation. For this, first of all, it is necessary to educate the new generation of personnel who will be

proactive reformers, who will think strategically, and who will be educated and qualified. That's why we started reforming all stages of education, from kindergarten to higher education" [2]. Because the role of education as an important factor of development is increasing in today's conditions, where the level and quality of life of the population has become the main indicator of the country's competitiveness in many ways. At present, society and civilizations are primarily competing with social values and educational systems" [3]. Therefore, one of the urgent tasks is to develop a general outlook of society and to form a rational attitude to nature through the development of continuous education.

In modern pedagogy, the need to form ecological knowledge and skills is increasing based on the improvement of the ecological education system. Because it is important methodologically important to study the causes of worsening the environmental situation, in particular, the characteristics of the spiritual and moral "impoverishment" of the society based on a new approach. In this case, the main task of forming ecological value is not only to evaluate embodied ecological theories and historical experiences from the point of view of the current era, to teach them to draw appropriate conclusions. Therefore, it is necessary to establish an integrative approach and cooperation of disciplines in the development of environmental competence among students, to use its possibilities in the pedagogical process and in the formation of social opinion.

In the development of environmental competence in students, it is necessary to form their ecological way of thinking based on the analysis of global environmental problems. The spiritual directions of human civilization form an internal unity within the framework of ecological problems, their legal and administrative directions are integrated, universal moral norms take priority in their function, and the norms and principles of moral value become the main factor in the regulation of human ecological activities. In contrast to the socio-political elements in the management of "nature-human" relations, moral and spiritual values are a unique activity that relies on the will of people. Eco-ethical competence is manifested in practical activities of students in nature protection. Therefore, environmental activities cannot be understood outside of the students' subjective aspirations, free will, and their socio-spiritual efforts. After all, ecological activity and responsibility manifests the needs of society.

Educational content, curriculum, programs, educational form, method, tools and textbooks, electronic information educational resources and other didactic materials, educational and methodological manuals, laboratory equipment, determined based on the use of educational technologies and others.

Qualified pedagogical practice will be organized in order for students to implement pedagogical activities in the future, apply practical skills in real conditions based on theoretical knowledge and psychomotor activities. Demonstration of environmental competences acquired by students in the educational process; in the course of pedagogical activity, activity monitoring was carried out to determine and analyze the preparation of qualified personnel with environmental competence.

The rich spiritual and cultural heritage and national values of the Uzbek people are important in developing the highest human qualities, including environmental competence, in future pedagogues. The ecological scientific conclusions of Uzbek thinkers and pedagogues, which have ensured the development of world science, have a special place among national values due to their pedagogical (educational) ecological nature. The use of scientific pedagogical views on ecology, which were put forward by them and helped to develop the attitude of respect for nature over the centuries, a positive attitude towards the environment in the minds of students, and a sense of responsibility for nature protection, and even today, ecological education it is considered an important ideological basis for effective education and development of environmental competence in future pedagogues.

Ecological values are the driving motive for the development of ecological competence in students and the formation of a system of ecological ethical relations in them, and a careful attitude to nature. Ecological values are manifested in the form of universal principles, norms, laws and ideals of society, and are a factor that directs the practical activity of the subject in nature protection. After all, ecological ethics "perceives the material world as a living being like a person, recognizes the fact that the universe is a great divine gift for man and is worthy of it, looks at nature, its high and conscious man with respect, generation, struggle for the purity of nations, land, air, and water" [4]. Therefore, the formation and development of ecological moral values is a condition for the rational organization of the use of natural resources. In this case, norms, laws, requirements, criteria, principles, etc. of universal value related to the management of environmental activities are interdependent according to their functional content. Therefore, on the basis of integrated education, it will be possible to develop students' ecological knowledge, to humanize their outlook on the basis of social sciences, and thereby to form in them respect for ecological values and an attitude towards their preservation.

It is necessary to get rid of the old way of thinking that there are no strict punishments for anti-environmental attitudes and actions in students, to inculcate in them the existence of strict punishments for the violation of environmental moral rules. The level of responsibility for the anti-ecological behavior against nature is not clearly defined in the legal norms, official acts, and the complex of laws. For example, the damage caused to some natural components cannot be prohibited by certain legal laws and acts. But these actions are controlled by universal ecological norms and public opinion. Their effectiveness lies in the fact that they connect with everyday, ordinary levels of social consciousness and become a way of life. Accordingly, in all nations, concepts such as "evil", "sin", "shame", which condemn negative attitudes towards nature, are used equally with them, even if they are not written in the laws. It is important to instill such ecological traditions and values from a young age, and to create teaching mechanisms in harmony with ethics in higher education.

Teaching students various principles of ecological values and increasing their importance of ecological values for the social environment and environmental protection. The axiological-regulatory function of ecological values is the norms and principles of encouragement or prohibition, which are the coordination of personal and social interests. In turn, these constitute the content of the student's ecological beliefs and determine the value directions of nature protection activities. The transformation of these requirements into the content of concrete practical activities depends on the student's understanding of his environmental responsibility and management and control of his activities based on public opinion. If members of society do not create "collective ecological ethics" of environmental protection, it will be very difficult for any measures to manage their activities based on environmental requirements to have a positive effect.

It is also important to develop environmental competence in students and to form environmental responsibility in them. The most important condition for managing ecological activities with the help of moral regulators is that every student has a deep sense of moral responsibility for nature and the future of society. From this point of view, ecological ethical responsibility fulfills two interrelated tasks. That is, firstly, through integrative education, it coordinates the subjective capabilities of the student with the objective necessity. Secondly, it shows its will in a humanized form, taking into account the social interests of students. Accordingly, environmental moral responsibility should be considered

as a social phenomenon that limits the free will of a person, which consists in changing nature at the same time, and encourages the activity of nature protection.

Development of environmental competence in students based on integrative education is preparation for environmental activities. Ecological activity is a complex social phenomenon, like other types of activity. Based on the concrete tasks of ecological activity forms, the subject's ability to choose certain ethical norms depends on the level of development of the society. Because at certain stages of society's development, the evil done to nature is morally justified. Even condemning elderly parents or sick people to forced death was considered a moral norm. It should be noted that ecological moral norms, as a subjective means of managing the balance of the biosphere, can be used consciously or spontaneously by a person. In this case, the conscious or spontaneous nature of ecological activity corresponds to the level of development of society. Therefore, by developing an ecological worldview in students, it will be possible to prepare them for changing ecological activities, values, traditions, and to form the skills of quick adaptation to changing conditions.

Any society, in a certain sense, abandons anti-ecological behavior that harms the life of future generations and prohibits sacrificing the interests of future generations to the needs of people living now. created a set of norms. In turn, these norms are relatively independent phenomena that differ from each other in the process of the objective development of nature, based on the material and spiritual needs of man, maintain the internal ecological balance of the biosphere, and anthropotechnogenic influence on nature. Environmental ethics' conscious and purposeful management of these relationships reveals its subjectivity. However, according to its genesis, the objectivity of environmental ethics also comes from the objectivity of human nature protection needs.

CONCLUSION.

Although there is a great need for this nowadays, a system that provides general ecological knowledge to students has not been created. Such a complex of knowledge is emerging in a fragmentary and partial way in the process of teaching natural sciences, technical, social and humanitarian sciences in educational institutions. In order to successfully solve the problem of formation and development of environmental responsibility in students, it is necessary to create a general theoretical concept of it, harmonizing all directions of education, and gradually and continuously implement this system.

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